

*38th International Electric Vehicle Symposium and Exhibition (EVS38)
Göteborg, Sweden, June 15-18, 2025*

Financial Impact Analysis of Electric Vehicle Charging Behavior with RNN Model and Validation Against Real-World Data

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Executive Summary

This study investigates the economic and environmental impacts of solar-optimized EV charging and explores the feasibility of predicting long-term charger behavior from short-term test data. Using standardized testing procedures developed in the "Wallbox-Inspektion" project, two commercial charging systems were analyzed. A Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (BiGRU) model, a specialized Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), was developed to predict five-hour charging behavior based on five-minute operational data. The results show that for systems with consistent control characteristics, long-term performance can be accurately predicted from short-term measurements. However, prediction accuracy decreases for chargers with irregular behavior. This approach offers the potential to significantly reduce testing time and associated costs, supporting faster development and certification of efficient, solar-optimized charging solutions.

Keywords: Electric Vehicles, AI - Artificial intelligence for EVs, Smart charging, Environmental Impact, Energy management

1 Introduction

The rapid growth of electric vehicle (EV) adoption necessitates efficient and reliable charging infrastructure. As the number of electric vehicles in Germany continues to increase, the number of charging stations for homeowners is growing correspondingly. Many homeowners possess both a photovoltaic (PV) system and a wallbox, aiming to charge their electric vehicles with energy from their PV system for both economic and environmental reasons. Additionally, smart meter charging reduces the grid impact from charging processes[1].

Solar surplus charging, also known as solar optimized charging, is a specific and increasingly popular form of smart charging in residential settings. In this approach, electric vehicles are charged exclusively with surplus energy from a photovoltaic (PV) system, after all other household loads have been supplied. This method is both economically and environmentally advantageous: homeowners benefit from lower energy costs compared to grid electricity, and grid operators are relieved from providing additional power. As electric mobility scales up, the integration of EV charging with residential energy systems, particularly through solar surplus charging, becomes essential. However, comparisons of different home energy management systems (HEMS) combined with EV charging stations reveal significant differences in control quality[1]

Previous studies have not thoroughly investigated the process of solar optimized charging, especially regarding signal processing delays from the charging station to the electric vehicle. These delays or dead times have a substantial impact on the charging process as they influence the efficiency of energy utilization[13, 14]. The charging station's time to adjust the set current requested from the charger and the vehicle's time to adapt the current from the charging station are crucial parameters. Additionally, the delay time of phase changes (from single phase to three phases or vice versa) is vital to optimally utilize the supplied energy from the solar system.

This study is conducted as part of the "Wallbox-Inspektion" project, which develops and applies standardized testing methodologies for EV chargers to enable robust evaluation of charger performance and its financial and environmental implications. The application test data, collected within this project, forms the basis for developing a Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (BiGRU) model, a specialized type of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), to predict charger behavior over a 5-hour period using only 5-minute operational data segments from three-phase charging scenarios with symmetrical load conditions.

Our research addresses two fundamental questions:

- *What are the quantifiable economic and environmental impacts of solar optimized charging over a 5-hour evaluation period, based on application test results?*
- *Can short-term application testing (5 minutes) provide reliable predictions of long-term charger behavior (5 hours) through the development of a BiGRU model?*

The analysis focuses on the charging system's ability to follow the household current ($-I_{House}$) through the control pilot current (I_{CP}), which directly correlates with operational costs and renewable energy integration efficiency[1]. By comparing predicted versus actual I_{CP} values over a 5-hour period, we assess the validity of using brief 5-minute test sequences to characterize long-term charging behavior. This approach allows us to evaluate how accurately the BiGRU model can predict the charger's response to varying surplus power conditions, which ultimately determines grid energy consumption and PV surplus utilization.

2 Test Environment

Field testing of charging systems lacks standardization and involves various system components, making comparison of trial results difficult. To address this, a test environment is established where solar charging systems are measured, incorporating essential components such as EV supply equipment (EVSE), HEMS, and an energy meter, as advised by the manufacturer. This setup simulates real-world conditions using Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) at the Digital Grid Lab at Fraunhofer ISE[4]. The test setup includes power terminals, power flows, and communications within the tested system. This includes power measurements M_{net} , M_{EV} , and M_{House} with their positive direction marked and the IEC 61851 communication. As real power flows are measured, the tested system is connected to the public grid which is tracked by M_{net} . Furthermore, the household is emulated by a bidirectional load emulation of the type Cinergia, with the resulting power flow measured by M_{House} . The EV is emulated by a digital twin called "ev twin" developed by Fraunhofer ISE in the HIL environment typhoon HIL. It emulates the charging process according to IEC 61851 and allows full Power-HIL testing and access to all model parameters[5, 2, 3]. This enables totally reproducible test results, decoupling the charging system test from influences of the EV. Among the model parameters are the results of the control pilot (CP) signal evaluation, which communicates the maximum allowed current I_{CP} to the EV[5].

3 Test Procedure

The test environment allows the EV charging system for private households to be fully tested. The charging station's power set point P_{CP} follows the residual load reference $-P_{House}$. P_{CP} is derived from the current set point I_{CP} using the voltages at M_{House} , as the charging station communicates current set points. In contrast to uncontrolled charging, solar charging must react to the fluctuating nature of PV surplus and requires a fast and accurate reaction of the HEMS. Hence, the control quality test evaluates the settling time towards a new maximum charging current set point. The expected reaction follows a change in the current $-I_{House}$. A decrease in $-I_{House}$ results in an increase in the permissible charging current for the EV I_{CP} . To assess control quality, several quantities need to be measured: the trigger event, which is the change in $-I_{House}$; the dead time t_D until the first change in the CP signal; the settling time t_S from the trigger event to a steady state; and after a waiting time, I_{CP} is recorded for an interval t_{mes} . During that interval, I_{CP} is compared to the expected current $-I_{House}$, and the control deviation $\Delta I_{CP} = I_{House} - I_{CP}$ is calculated [1].

Figure 1: Test environment for evaluating system reactions for solar controlled charging including the emulated grid, EV, and house. Positive measurement directions are marked.

3.1 Control Quality Test

The control quality test is designed to evaluate the charging system's ability to respond to changes in the residual load reference. In this test, the charging station's power set point P_{CP} is expected to follow the residual load reference $-P_{House}$. The test procedure involves applying a series of step changes to $-I_{House}$ and measuring the system's response. For each step change, the test measures the dead time t_D (the time between the step change and the first observed change in the CP signal), the settling time t_S (the time from the step change to when the system reaches a steady state), and the control deviation ΔI_{CP} (the difference between the expected current $-I_{House}$ and the actual current I_{CP}). The test is repeated for 17 set points of $-I_{House}$ for both single and three-phase charging, with step sizes ranging from 0.5 A to 16 A to anticipate different charging scenarios. This comprehensive approach allows for a detailed characterization of the charging system's control quality across a wide range of operating conditions[1].

3.2 Application Test

While the control quality test determines system behavior in an artificial scenario, the application test observes the systems' behavior in a real-world scenario. Residual load time series data with 1-second resolution is applied to $-P_{House}$. This data was previously measured in a field system. The ability of the charging systems' set point P_{CP} to follow the reference is quantified through the parameters $E_{feed-in}$ and E_{draw} . $E_{feed-in}$ is the amount of surplus energy fed into the grid, while E_{draw} is the amount of energy drawn from the grid due to control imperfections. Two parameters are chosen to allow for differentiated weighting, as drawing from the grid implicates higher costs. In an optimal scenario where the controller follows the reference perfectly, both parameters would evaluate to zero. Additionally, E_{EV} (the total charged energy) and E_{House} (the total PV generated energy) are calculated.

For the 5-minute application test, a section with residual power between 5 kW and 12.5 kW is chosen to test the chargers. For this 5-minute test only, E_{House} should theoretically be the same in all test runs as the same time series data is used but can vary slightly due to fluctuations in the voltage when current set points are given. However, for the 5-hour data tests, $-P_{House}$ is not the same across test runs[1].

4 BiGRU Model Development

4.1 Data Collection

We utilize data from application tests conducted on EV chargers, focusing on real-world residual load time series. These tests capture the charging system's ability to follow the household current ($-I_{House}$) through the control pilot current (I_{CP}) [1]. The dataset includes 5-minute operational phases of three-phase charging with symmetrical load conditions, providing a foundation for predicting 5-hour charging behavior.

The BiGRU-based approach has demonstrated superior performance for short-term electric load forecasting compared to traditional methods, particularly for mid- to long-term prediction horizons [17]. This makes it especially suitable for our application in predicting EV charging behavior.

4.2 Model Architecture

We employ a Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (BiGRU) network to capture temporal dependencies in sequential charging data. The bidirectional architecture enables the model to process information from both past and future states, improving prediction accuracy by extracting more comprehensive temporal patterns [17]. Our architecture includes:

- Three stacked BiGRU layers with 128, 64, and 32 units, respectively, allowing the model to capture multi-scale temporal dynamics. Each BiGRU layer is followed by dropout (rate=0.3) for regularization.
- Two dense layers with batch normalization process the extracted features before the final output layer.
- L2 regularization (1×10^{-5}) is applied to prevent overfitting during training.

The BiGRU architecture was selected for its ability to process sequences in both directions, capturing comprehensive temporal patterns that are critical for accurate current prediction. Compared to traditional LSTM networks, BiGRU offers computational efficiency while maintaining strong predictive performance for time series forecasting tasks [18].

4.3 Training Methodology

The dataset undergoes preprocessing, including outlier removal using the Interquartile Range (IQR) method [19] and feature engineering to enhance model performance. The IQR threshold is set to 1.5 to effectively remove extreme peaks and outliers while preserving the main data range.

Training data consists of 300-second segments, and the optimal sequence length is determined through validation testing. The model is trained using a custom time derivative loss function that combines mean squared error with derivative regularization to reduce prediction delay:

$$\mathcal{L} = \alpha \cdot \text{MSE}(y_{\text{true}}, y_{\text{pred}}) + \beta \cdot \text{MSE}(y'_{\text{true}}, y'_{\text{pred}}) \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha = 0.8$, $\beta = 0.2$, and y' represents the time derivative of the signal.

Training is performed with early stopping (patience of 25 epochs), learning rate reduction on plateau, and a step decay learning rate scheduler to optimize convergence [20]. An ensemble of BiGRU models with varied hyperparameters is also trained, and their predictions are averaged to improve robustness and accuracy.

4.4 Performance Evaluation

Model performance is evaluated using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which quantifies the average magnitude of prediction errors by measuring the square root of the mean squared difference between predicted and actual values [21]:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

RMSE provides a straightforward interpretation of average error in the same units as the target variable, making it easier to communicate model performance. It also penalizes more significant errors more heavily, which is appropriate for our charging system, where considerable prediction errors could lead to operational issues.

4.5 Prediction Validation

Predictions are validated through comprehensive error analysis:

- Energy error quantifies the percentage difference between actual and predicted energy consumption:

$$\text{Energy Error} = \frac{|E_{\text{actual}} - E_{\text{predicted}}|}{E_{\text{actual}}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

where $E = \sum I \cdot \Delta t$ represents the integrated current over time.

- Visual validation includes plotting actual versus predicted I_{CP} values alongside input $-I_{House}$ data to evaluate the model's ability to track dynamic changes.

Both RMSE and energy error are computed on the test set, measuring the difference between actual and predicted I_{CP} values. This provides a robust assessment of model generalization and real-world predictive accuracy.

5 Financial Impact

The financial model evaluates the energy consumption of the charging session and translates it into associated costs based on a fixed electricity pricing scheme. The economic impact is determined by comparing the residual load $-P_{House}$ with the actual charging power P_{CP} throughout the charging process.

At each time step, specific conditions are applied to determine the associated costs. If $P_{CP} \leq -P_{House}$, the charging is fully supplied by surplus PV energy, resulting in no additional electricity costs. However, if:

$$\begin{cases} P_{CP} > -P_{House} \\ I_{CP_{\min}} < -I_{House} < I_{CP_{\max}} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

then the difference between the charging power and the available PV surplus must be drawn from the grid, and the corresponding cost is calculated as:

$$\text{Financial Impact} = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(P_{CP,t} + P_{House,t})\Delta t}{3600000} \times 0.30 \quad (5)$$

where €0.30/kWh represents the average electricity purchase price in Germany in 2023 [16].

The conditions on $I_{CP_{\min}}$ and $I_{CP_{\max}}$ account for the technical operating limits of the charger. In practice, the Device Under Test (DUT) can only operate within a specific range of charging currents: for both DUTs, the minimum permissible charging current is 6 A, while the maximum is 16 A for DUT #1 and 32 A for DUT #2. When the residual load $-I_{House}$ falls outside the interval $[I_{CP_{\min}}, I_{CP_{\max}}]$, the charger is physically unable to adapt its charging current to match the available surplus. To ensure a fair evaluation, periods where $-I_{House}$ lies outside $[I_{CP_{\min}}, I_{CP_{\max}}]$ are excluded from the financial impact calculation. This approach ensures that the assessment focuses solely on the charger's performance within its controllable operating limits, avoiding penalties for conditions where adaptation is technically impossible.

6 Environmental Impact

The environmental impact is calculated based on the CO₂ emissions associated with the grid electricity consumed during charging. Using the same conditions as the financial model, we calculate:

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ Emissions} = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(P_{CP,t} + P_{House,t})\Delta t}{3600000} 0.354 \quad (6)$$

Where 0.354 represents the CO₂ emissions factor for the German electricity mix in 2023 (354 grams of CO₂ per kilowatt-hour)[15].

Additionally, the energy impact calculated in kWh:

$$\text{Energy Impact} = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(P_{CP,t} + P_{House,t})\Delta t}{3600000} \quad (7)$$

This comprehensive model allows us to evaluate both the economic and environmental benefits of different charging strategies and the impact of control quality on overall charging performance. By comparing the financial and environmental metrics of varying charging systems, we can identify the most cost-effective and environmentally friendly solutions for solar optimized charging.

7 Results

7.1 Prediction Results

The BiGRU model demonstrates varying degrees of success in predicting charger behavior based on 5-minute operational data segments. The performance varies significantly between the two DUTs, highlighting the challenges in developing a universal prediction model for EV charging systems.

7.1.1 DUT #1

As shown in Figures 2 and 3, DUT #1 exhibits relatively consistent behavior during both short-term (300 seconds) and long-term (20000 seconds) operation. The charging current (I_{CP}) closely follows the reference current ($-I_{House}$) with minimal delay and overshoot. Figure 4 demonstrates that our BiGRU model successfully captures this behavior, with predicted values closely matching actual measurements.

The quantitative evaluation of the model's performance for DUT #1 yields an RMSE of 3.8024 and an Energy Error of 4.9559%. This indicates that the model can predict the charging behavior with high accuracy, resulting in reliable energy consumption estimates over the 5-hour period. The low energy error demonstrates that despite some point-by-point deviations, the overall energy prediction remains accurate, which is crucial for financial and environmental impact assessments.

Figure 2: Short-term (300 seconds) operational data for DUT #1.

Figure 3: Long-term (20000 seconds) operational data for DUT #1.

Figure 4: Comparison of actual and BiGRU-predicted I_{CP} for DUT #1 in relation to $-I_{House}$.

7.1.2 DUT #2

DUT #2 (Figures 5 and 6) exhibits more complex behavior, particularly in the long-term test where significant current peaks and inconsistent response patterns are observed. As seen in Figure 7, the BiGRU model struggles to fully capture this irregular behavior, resulting in substantial prediction errors.

The quantitative evaluation for DUT #2 shows an RMSE of 15.5730 and an Energy Error of 44.1291%. These high error metrics indicate that the model fails to predict the charging behavior of this device accurately. The substantial energy error suggests that the predicted energy consumption would significantly differ from the actual consumption, making financial and environmental impact predictions unreliable for this device.

Figure 5: Short-term (300 seconds) operational data for DUT #2.

Figure 6: Long-term (20000 seconds) operational data for DUT #2.

Figure 7: Comparison of actual and BiGRU-predicted I_{CP} for DUT #2 in relation to $-I_{House}$.

7.2 Analysis of Prediction Performance Variability

The stark contrast in prediction accuracy between the two devices under test highlights several important factors that influence the predictability of charging behavior. Our analysis reveals several technical reasons for these differences:

7.2.1 Dead Time and Settling Time

The measurements reveal significant delays in responding to changes in surplus power. During these periods, the I_{CP} cannot track rapid changes in $-I_{House}$. DUT #1 demonstrates relatively consistent and shorter response times, while DUT #2 exhibits longer and more variable delays, making its behavior more difficult to predict from short-term data samples.

7.2.2 Phase Switching Delays

When switching between single-phase and three-phase charging, there are substantial off times where charging stops completely before resuming in the new phase configuration. These transition periods introduce discontinuities in the charging profile that are challenging for the BiGRU model to capture, especially when they occur infrequently in the training data but more frequently in the test data.

7.2.3 Minimum Charging Thresholds

The dynamic test results show that charging stops or continues with a current higher than the surplus current when the surplus current drops below certain thresholds (approximately 6A per phase), indicating there are minimum power requirements for charging to occur. These non-linear behaviors, particularly when they manifest differently across devices, create additional complexity for the prediction model.

7.2.4 Control Algorithm Differences

The fundamental difference in prediction accuracy can be attributed to the underlying control algorithms implemented in each device. DUT #1 employs a more consistent and predictable control strategy that closely tracks the reference current with minimal deviation. In contrast, DUT #2 appears to implement a more complex control algorithm with variable response characteristics that change based on operating conditions, making its behavior more difficult to predict from limited training data.

7.3 Economic and Environmental Impact Analysis

Tables 1 and 2 present the actual and predicted impacts of the charging sessions for DUT #1 and DUT #2, respectively. For DUT #1, our model provides reasonably accurate predictions of energy consumption (1.98 kWh vs. 2.18 kWh actual), CO₂ emissions (0.70 kg vs. 0.77 kg actual), and financial impact (0.58 € vs. 0.60 € actual). This represents prediction errors of 8.7%, 9.1%, and 3.3% respectively, which are

acceptable for practical applications.

In contrast, DUT #2 predictions show significant deviations from actual measurements, with substantial differences in all impact metrics. This highlights the challenges in predicting long-term behavior for devices with complex control algorithms or irregular response patterns.

These results demonstrate that while BiGRU models can effectively predict long-term charging behavior from short-term data for systems with consistent control characteristics (as seen with DUT #1), their accuracy diminishes for systems with irregular behavior or variable response patterns (as observed with DUT #2). This finding has important implications for the development of standardized testing methodologies, suggesting that different approaches may be needed for different types of charging systems.

Table 1: Economic and Environmental Impacts for DUT #1 (5-Hour Session)

	Energy Impact [kWh]	CO ₂ Emissions [kg]	Financial Impact [€]
Actual	2.18	0.77	0.60
Predicted	1.98	0.70	0.58

Table 2: Economic and Environmental Impacts for DUT #2 (5-Hour Session)

	Energy Impact [kWh]	CO ₂ Emissions [kg]	Financial Impact [€]
Actual	35.17	12.66	10.47
Predicted	7.60	2.13	2.13

8 Conclusion

This study investigated the economic and environmental impacts of solar-optimized EV charging and evaluated the feasibility of predicting long-term charger behavior from short-term test data using BiGRU models. Our findings demonstrate that:

- Solar-optimized charging can significantly reduce grid energy consumption, with corresponding economic and environmental benefits when implemented with appropriate control systems. The tested devices showed varying degrees of effectiveness in utilizing PV surplus energy.
- BiGRU models can successfully predict long-term (5-hour) charging behavior from short-term (5-minute) test data for systems with consistent control characteristics, as demonstrated by the DUT #1 results with an Energy Error of only 4.9559%.
- Prediction accuracy is significantly affected by system irregularities and control algorithm complexity, as seen with DUT #2 where the Energy Error reached 44.1291%.
- The model's performance is heavily influenced by technical factors including dead time, settling time, phase switching delays, and minimum charging thresholds that vary between different charging systems.
- Standardized testing methodologies are essential for reliable comparison of different charging systems, enabling objective evaluation of their economic and environmental impacts.

The stark difference in prediction accuracy between the two devices highlights a fundamental challenge in EV charging infrastructure: not all charging systems can follow the desired current profile with the same precision. This variability stems from differences in control algorithms, hardware capabilities, and design philosophies among manufacturers.

Our analysis reveals that successful solar-optimized charging requires charging systems that can quickly and accurately respond to changes in surplus power. Systems with significant dead times, long settling times, or substantial phase switching delays will inevitably be less efficient at utilizing available solar energy, resulting in higher grid energy consumption and associated costs.

These results have important implications for the development and evaluation of solar-optimized charging systems. The ability to predict long-term behavior from short-term tests can significantly reduce testing time and costs, accelerating the development and certification of efficient charging solutions.

However, care must be taken to ensure data quality and to account for potential system irregularities.

Future work should focus on improving model robustness against data anomalies, expanding the testing to include a wider range of charging systems and operational scenarios, and developing standardized certification procedures based on the testing methodologies presented in this paper. Additionally, manufacturers should prioritize reducing response times and improving control algorithms to support solar-optimized charging applications better.

Acknowledgments

The work in this contribution has been supported by project "Wallbox-Inspektion", funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate in the funding scheme "Elektro Mobil" (FKZ: 01MV23027).

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Presenter Biography

Since 2024, Deniz Pekmezci has been working as a researcher at the Department of "Smart Grids" at Fraunhofer ISE, focusing on bidirectional charging technologies. She holds a Master's degree in Chemical and Energy Engineering from Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg, completed in 2024. During her studies, she worked at the Max Planck Institute for Dynamics of Complex Technical Systems, where she also conducted her master's thesis.